

Being Othered: The Representation of Tourette Syndrome in Select Works

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ABSTRACT

Tourette Syndrome (TS) is a neurological disorder characterised by repetitive, involuntary movements and vocalisations called tics. The attitude of society towards the disabled has changed slightly due to the books and movies which present the theme of disability. The paper analyses in detail *Front of the Class: How Tourette Syndrome Made Me the Teacher I Never Had*, an autobiography written by Brad Cohen who is a teacher with Tourette Syndrome. The paper also throws light on complex tics or behaviours like Coprolalia, Copropraxia and Echolalia as reflected in the movies *Niagara Niagara* and *The Road Within*.

INTRODUCTION

According to Lennard J. Davies, the “problem” of disability does not lie with the person with disabilities but rather in the way normalcy is constructed. “The concept of a norm, unlike that of an ideal, implies that the majority of the population must or should somehow be part of the norm” (Davis 3). Davis further states that an important consequence of the idea of the norm is that it divides the total population into standard and non-standard subpopulations. A person who is different from the norms of the majority is treated as the other. Hence, a person who does not articulate or behave according to the standard set by society is termed disabled.

In 1825, a Tourette Syndrome case was identified by a well-known doctor, Jean Marc Gaspard Itard, in the patient La Marquise de Dampierre, who had Coprolalia and other behavioural diseases. Later, Dr Georges Gilles de la Tourette followed the clinical practice of the Father of Neurology, Jean Martin Charcot. In 1885, Dr Georges Gilles de la Tourette published studies on a rare disease describing nine cases “affected by multiple tics, especially involving the face, superiority in the arts, and uncontrollable verbal bursts including insults and profanities”(Dina and Porta 2). The term tic was first used in veterinary medicine to describe horses’ pathologic breathing. The horse makes the sound tic when it hits the wood of the stable with its teeth and is bothered by the air in its stomach. The situation of la Marquise de Dampierre, as stated by Itard and 60 years later by

Georges Gilles de la Tourette, is compiled by Dina and Porta :

At the age of 7, she had onset of symptoms: severe mouth, face, neck and arm tics. Shouts, insults and obscenity bursts appear some years later. Because of these problems, the noble woman spent her life segregated in her palace until her death. Her speech would suddenly be interrupted with shouts, swearing and unexpected words, despite her high intelligence and good manners. When she was with other people, she used to inappropriately describe others, causing embarrassment to all bystanders. The more she was scandalised by her own explicitness and by the repetition of these vulgarities, the more these words were “forced” onto her tongue and she couldn't control herself. (3-5)

Tourette Syndrome is not only characterised by tics, but also by behavioural symptoms. Many with TS also have attention deficit disorder (ADD), Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), and Obsessive Compulsive Disorder (OCD). Tics are repetitive, non rhythmic and involuntary movements which may be motor tics or sound tics. Tics may be classified into clonic tics, dystonic tics and tonic tics. Blinking is an example of clonic tics. Whereas teeth grinding and arm stretching are examples of dystonic tics and tonic tics, respectively. Tics may vary in relation to typology, complexity, frequency, intensity, interference and social impairment. The premonitory urge is a physical or psychological sensation that signals the arrival of a tic. (Dina and Porta 37)

Brad Cohen, author of *Front of the Class: How Tourette Syndrome Made Me the Teacher I Never Had*, is a motivational speaker and the recipient of Georgia's First Class Teacher of the Year Award. As a person with Tourette Syndrome, he was humiliated in public spaces as “barking kid”, “kid with hiccups”, “unacceptable kid”, “rebellious, willful kid”, “troublemaker” and so on. Brad admits that he enjoys short-lived, blissful moments, but he also realises that he is not normal. “As a child, I even heard adults openly speculate as to whether my behavior meant that the devil possessed me. Today people routinely stare at me in the mall, going to a movie or concert is virtually impossible, and dating is a whole other story in itself. I am one of over a hundred thousand people in the United States who have full-blown Tourette syndrome” (Cohen). *Front of the Class: How Tourette Syndrome Made Me the*

Teacher I Never Had, has been successfully adapted to movies: *Front of the Class* and *Hitchki*.

Niagra Niagra, directed by Bob Gosse, portrays Marcy, the heroine who suffers from Tourette Syndrome. She meets Seth on a shoplifting spree. Marcy tries to suppress her tics while talking to Seth by drinking alcohol and beating the floor without his notice. Her helplessness in losing his company is reflected in her behaviour. Marcy is disappointed as there is no black Barbie in the store. Marcy and Seth are not able to accept the racism which is evident even in the collection of toys available in supermarkets. Seth is willing to accompany her to Canada to buy a black Barbie. Seth is surprised to see her spacious house and also a messy truck transformed into her room. They pack some essential items required for travel from her house. From the conversation, it is clear that her parents are affluent, though we do not get a chance to see them on the screen. She says that alcohol and sex enable her to suppress tics. Marcy and Seth are not able to purchase whiskey as they are under 21. The pharmacists are not ready to provide her medicines for Tourette Syndrome as she does not have the prescription with her. Even from her behaviour and muscle tics, they did not realise the emergency situation of consuming tablets to avoid tics. The immediacy of obtaining drugs forces them to rob medicines from the pharmacy. Marcy does not have any control over her actions, as she even attacks the friendly Walter, who gave them shelter and food. When a police officer visits Walter to enquire about Marcy and Seth, who had robbed the pharmacy, Walter wisely denies it to protect the young couple. The inability of Seth is reflected when he leaves the bleeding Walter unattended. Finally, when Marcy and Seth reach Canada, Marcy is shot dead by a cop. Only Seth was able to understand her strange tantrums, and he roams alone after her demise. These youngsters develop alcoholism and engage in malpractices and crime like shoplifting and physical attacks, as they did not get parental or peer support. Only through awareness can parents, teachers, siblings and peer groups understand disability and support people with disability. Brad was lucky enough to have a mother who constantly stood with him, though she had problems related to being a single parent.

The Road Within, directed by Gren Wells, portrays the lives of three teenagers forced to stay in a rehabilitation centre because they are deemed abnormal. In the rehabilitation centre, Vincent, who suffers from Tourette Syndrome, shares a room

with Alex, a clean freak. He shouts at Vincent when he enters the room wearing shoes. Marie, who suffers from anorexia nervosa, is instructed to take Vincent around the rehabilitation centre. Vincent and Marie create a strong bond and plan to run away from the rehabilitation centre. Alex notices them escaping with his CDs in the car of the doctor, Rose. In order to avoid being noticed by the inmates, Vincent and Marie drag and kidnap the screaming Alex. During their road journey, the clean freak Alex, who suffers from Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder, compromises and adjusts with others. Meanwhile, they are able to create a strong bond among themselves, though initially their inability to cope was a hindrance. The three youngsters with behavioural issues are able to realise their inner capacities to solve life issues when they open the road within themselves, as the title of the film suggests. The problem arises only when they are judged through the yardsticks of the “normal”. According to Gren Wells, the director of the film, people with Tourette Syndrome are made fun of. She says that there is a big difference between laughing at someone and laughing with someone. Brad Cohen tries to overcome the situation by transforming the embarrassing situations into laughter. He states, “Laughing also shows that you are comfortable with your disability, and if you are comfortable, others around you will relax”.

HUMILIATION IN PUBLIC SPACES

Touretters will not be able to perform certain tasks which are quite normal. As the term syndrome has a negative connotation, another term used to refer to them is ‘Touretic patient’ as suggested by Jo Bervoets, Diana Beljaars and Hanne De Jaegher. Reading is a passive skill; anyone who knows the language may be able to read. But reading is a troublesome activity for Brad as he admits, “Reading an entire chapter in a textbook was like running a race with cinderblocks strapped to my ankles.” When many Touretters think of suicide, Brad’s approach was positive. His optimistic nature is reflected in his words, “There was some gift inside my nature that allowed me to tolerate my high-maintenance constant companion.” Brad recalls that during a closing ceremony at the end of the summer camp, his counsellor gave him an improvised “Froggy Award” for having amused everyone with his funny noises all season. Brad says, “I wasn’t upset by the tongue-in-cheek award or by the hand-lettered paper certificate”. Dina and Porta throw light on complex tics or behaviours associated with TS:

- a. Coprolalia: repetition of obscene word/s or sentences
- b. Copropraxia: repetition of obscene movements

- c. Echolalia: repetition of someone else's word/s
- d. Echopraxia: repetition of someone else's movements
- e. Palilalia: repetition of one's own utterance/s
- f. Handwriting tics: paligraphia, i.e. writing again and again the same letter/word/sentence
- g. Walking tics: leg tics while walking
- h. Non-Obscene Socially Inappropriate Behaviours (NOSI): inappropriate behaviours or tics related to the impulsivity of the TS sufferer, and they could have serious social consequences.
- i. Stuttering: speech with involuntary disruptions such as repetitions of sounds/syllables/words, or prolongation of sounds, or interruptions of speech.
- j. Change in the tone of voice: it manifests randomly, not only in relation to emotional changes.

In *Niagara, Niagara*, Marcy calls Seth, “son of a bitch” as she has the complex tic named Coprolalia. She also has Copropraxia, which is the repetition of obscene movements. She often touches and hits Seth out of context and drags the steering wheel while he drives. She cannot control her hands and her movements, and thereby she makes others uncomfortable. She repeats certain words, which is an indication that she has Palilalia. Vincent in *The Road Within* also has Coprolalia. In the church, in between the mass, Vincent utters abusive words which embarrass his father and stepmother. He runs out of the church saying, “Shut up, fucking paedophile.” “ Fuck”. The boy struggles to speak and gets irritated when his father expresses his plan to sell their home. At the same time, Vincent shares his desire to take his mother’s photo to the Ocean as she wanted. When the father makes fun of him, he says, “I’m not as helpless as you think”. According to his father, he cannot go even to 7-Eleven”. Even his father underestimates and insults him because he is not a normal child. The support of the parents is inevitable for people with Tourette Syndrome. But later, when Vincent travels with Marie and Alex, he is relaxed and not conscious of the tics.

Brad Cohen recalls how he was a distraction to everyone in the classroom and public spaces. When he was in fifth grade, his noises got much louder. “Woop! Ja, ja ... JA!” His classmates kept him at a distance, and “teachers had absolutely no patience with me. After one long series of barks, the teacher humiliated me by making me stand in front of his classmates and apologize for making noises. Then she made

me promise to stop. I didn't really understand why I needed to do this, but I got up anyway and stood tall in front of the class". He states that asking a person with TS to stop tics is similar to asking a person with an allergy not to sneeze. The helplessness of the boy is reflected in this confession. Brad could not argue with the teacher, though he knew classrooms should be safe places for children to learn, "but in this class, with this teacher, nothing was safe". The constant support of his mother is evident as she fought like a tiger on his behalf. "As much as the humiliation hurt, that teacher had a huge positive impact on my life. Because of that incident—and many others just like it—I eventually vowed that someday I, too, would become a teacher, but I would be the great teacher I never had".

The bullying by his classmates was traumatic for Brad. Tics got worse and worse, as his stress level increased, so did the number and volume of his tics.

"Woop, woop ... FA, fa, FA!" Kids routinely danced circles around me while I tried to eat. They imitated the noises I made and laughed at their own impersonations, while I stared into a tray of tasteless cafeteria food. I tried to ignore them and eat my lunch, but that was impossible. I was a sitting duck. Sometimes I tried to explain that I had Tourette syndrome, but they never listened. I guess it made them feel better to put someone else down. But it just made me want to go home. It also made me want to throw my food at them. I wanted to yell and scream in frustration and beat the tar out of them. But I didn't. I didn't do any of that because I knew it would just make it harder for me if I did. (Cohen)

How Brad resisted the adverse situation is really appreciative. When the kids insulted him during lunchtime, he went to the nurse's office. He was on Haldol, a medication he took for TS that caused both fatigue and an increase in appetite. He had to go to the nurse's office to get medication, and over time, the nurse and he developed a friendship of sorts. One day, she invited him into her office to eat lunch. "I can't tell you how grateful I was for this unexpected respite. One day turned into another, and then another. Pretty soon, eating in the nurse's office became a lunchtime habit and a much-needed break from the mockery and taunts of the other students." A comfortable space in an educational institution is the right of all students. The most enjoyable time for a child in school is the lunchtime, but unfortunately,

Brad was denied it because of tics. If students were educated to be more inclusive and accept individual differences, life would not have been problematic for Brad.

The school bus was another difficult place where Brad was insulted. To avoid that, his mother often drove him to school. After a fight between Brad and another boy, they were both suspended from school. “I was being punished for being attacked for something I couldn’t control. In-school suspension meant sitting in a little room with four white walls with nothing on them. Lunch was brought to you, and no noises of any kind were allowed. I did my best to observe the no-noise rule, but my best effort was a miserable failure.” The school becomes an unfair space. He also had worse situations with his math teacher, a tall, skinny man who towered over his students. He was a stern man who seldom smiled, and he had no tolerance for tics. “He thought I was doing “the hiccups” on purpose; he truly believed I could control them and that I was only ticcing to get attention. Not too far into the school year, he began putting me in time-out whenever my tics started to bother him, which was pretty much constantly. I was the perpetual “kid in the corner.”(Cohen)

Brad states that it is difficult for him to go to a movie because his “barking noises” distract other people. The Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) has ensured his right to attend public events such as movie showings. So he reschedules his off-peak time when there will not be a lot of people there who will be disturbed by his series of “woops and rah-rah’s”. Bar Mitzvah, a ninety-minute religious service, is one of the most significant events in the life of a Jewish boy, which Brad could manage perfectly. Brad states, “That’s a lot of pressure for any kid, and an almost impossible task for someone with Tourette’s”. He could also take part as one of the panellists in *The Sally Jesse Raphael Show*, filmed in St. Louis, which devoted an entire show to Tourette syndrome.

Of our little group, I was the most vocal with my tics—so vocal, in fact, that the producers were nervous that I would distract from the discussion panel, and they ended up pulling me from that part of the show. I can’t tell you the disappointment I felt. It was like being rejected from a group of rejects, and, at the time, I was really hurt. If the producers really wanted to show what Tourette’s was like, they should have embraced the fact that I was there. The goal of the show was to educate people about Tourette syndrome. For the

purpose of displaying Tourette's in both an audio and a visual setting, I should have been their perfect guest". (Cohen)

When Sally came into the audience and asked routine questions about TS, he was nervous. He states, "I can now watch the video of that show and see a plump, uncertain young boy with an Afro who was visibly struggling, but who did indeed turn out to be the ideal guest. I looked and sounded like a typical person with Tourette syndrome. Perfect."

The school principal, Bill Myer, changed the life of Brad Cohen to a great extent as he gave Brad the opportunity to speak about TS during an orchestra concert attended by the entire junior high. Brad explains his limitations and inability to control his tics, "You will notice that I—woop, woop—make my noises more when I am nervous, uncomfortable, under stress, in a new situation—RAH, rah, rah—and when I think about it," I said. "But when I am relaxed, not stressed, or around people I know, I—fa, FA ... woop—will not do it as much. I don't want to make—woop—these noises, but there is no cure at this—woop, woop—time, so this is what I do." Brad added that he only wanted to be treated like everyone else. He also mentioned that he was excited to share this information with them so they could understand why he made all the noises. As he handed the microphone back to the principal and began walking to his seat, all the people in the room began clapping. It boosted the confidence when he realised the applause was for him. "I could hardly believe it. Hundreds of kids were clapping for me just because I had gotten up in front of them and educated them about Tourette's. Talk about positive reinforcement—this was it" (Cohen). This instance changed the life of Brad. Unfortunately, Marcy and Vincent were not blessed to get such a support from their family or from their teachers.

FIGHTING BACK

Brad shares a very insulting experience which happened at a local restaurant, Tippins. As Brad and his friends tried to order, the manager told him that he had to stop making noises or he would be asked to leave, so Brad gave him his standard spiel about Tourette's: "Hi. I'm Brad, and the noises and tics I am making are because I have Tourette syndrome. Tourette syndrome is a neurological disorder that causes me to make noises and tics I can't control. I'm really open and honest about Tourette syndrome, so if you have any questions, please feel free to ask. Thank you." Later, the manager asked them to move into a corner because he was disturbing people. "It was a very awkward moment. It wasn't so much what the manager

asked us to do; it was the way he asked. He was very defensive and loud and turned the situation into a public scene. Usually, when I go out in public, and someone asks about Tourette's, I'll gladly educate him or her. Then, if the person still doesn't understand, my friends jump in. I've never talked with my friends about jumping in—it's just something they do spontaneously, and usually with far more passion than I". The insult was too much for Brad to bear. Brad called Tippins' headquarters in Kansas City and reported. The company executives were so apologetic and sent a gift certificate to have a complimentary meal. "I was pleased that they did the right thing. One of their employees messed up, but they did what they could to make amends. The best thing of all? There was no dollar amount on the certificate. We could order as much as we wanted. The first chance we got, I rounded up my friends and we ordered a feast. I, personally, made sure I had two pieces of pie. Sometimes there are advantages to having Tourette's." Brad's no-hate policy is the reason for his success.

A clerk asked Brad to leave Steak and Fries Restaurant when he was enjoying food with his friends from the new school. The clerk even threatened to call the police when the helpless Brad tried to explain his Tourette disorder. Brad felt very sad and wondered if he would constantly be judged on his tics and twitches rather than on his other qualities. His initial sorrow turned to anger and frustration. Astonishingly, he got good support from the people around his apartment. They started sending emails to Steak and Fries management informing them of the incident. They also suggested that the student population would be boycotting the place because of the discrimination shown to Brad. Later, the restaurant invited Brad and apologised to him in person. They were apologetic about the behaviour of the clerk and also gave him coupons for sandwiches. Kicking him out of public places was too traumatic and humiliating, whatever compensation they offered later. The degradation and discrimination Brad faced, were covered in *The Bradley Scout*, the newspaper of the university.

Brad had to struggle a lot to get a job. He first took on the role of a busboy at a popular restaurant. He was fired on the first day of the job; the restaurant had violated the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA). He hired a lawyer, who argued for the rights of the disabled. The courts ended up being favourable to him, and Brad won a small settlement. He had developed the habit of helping neighbours mowing lawns, shovelling snow or babysitting. With the strong ambition to be a teacher, he joined Bradley University. He was extremely thrilled and stated, "Bradley Cohen attending Bradley University had become a reality." In most of the interviews, Brad failed because the principals of the schools believed that Brad could not be a teacher because of TS. One of the principals said, "I just don't know

how you could teach”. In the continued conversation, the principal also says that he has never seen a teacher with TS. He feared that the students would make fun of Brad. The patience of Brad is reflected in his words, “I assure you, sir, that I can teach. In fact, I think I'm a better teacher because I have battled to overcome this disability. I was the student teacher, and I was very successful. Tourette wasn't the problem that you say it is. In fact, it wasn't a problem at all.” (Cohen)

CONCLUSION

The study has explored in detail issues related to Tourette Syndrome in *Front of the Class: How Tourette Syndrome Made Me the Teacher I Never Had*, *Niagara Niagara* and *The Road Within*. The attitude of Brad Cohen is different from that of Marcy and Vincent. They are very impulsive and immature, so they fail to deal with the insults. As Seth repeatedly informs Marcy, “The problem is not yours”, but of the illness. If the society is ready to accept them as they are, many issues would have been solved in their lives. More than physical ailments, the issues are related to the construction of normalcy. With strong determination, Brad was able to reach from the margin to the centre. The intensity of tics varies from person to person. There should be more inclusive platforms for people with disabilities at homes, schools and workplaces. The study has also analysed in detail the marginalisation, alienation, conflict and trauma the people with Tourette syndrome face. The educational institutions should develop inclusive practices and the public spaces should be open to everyone.

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